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D3-3 – Overview of transfer and conversion of PFAS during sediment treatment/valorisation

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Executive Summary

This document is the result of Subtask 3.2.1 “Overview of transfer and conversion of PFAS during sediment treatment” of WP3 of the PROMISCES project. Particularly, this report is documented by occurrence of PFAS, and their probable pathways in all fractions obtained during treatment and valorization of marine dredged sediments by the soil washing treatment ECOSEDRA.

The Italian Project ECOSEDRA has the purpose of creating and validating at demonstrative scale (TRL> 7) an innovative technological solution for the eco-sustainable management of sediments from port dredging operations. Particularly, within ECOSEDRA project, a prototype sediment treatment plant fed with 25-50 kg/h of dredged sludge from Ancona Sea port has been implemented to produce construction materials for reuse in road embankments. Hence, taking advantage of the concurrent ECOSEDRA project, PROMISCES has investigated fate and pathways of PFAS compounds during soil washing treatments. PFAS removal from dredged sediments has been investigated at laboratory scale during the design phase of the ECOSEDRA plant. Then, when the demo plant was in operation, fate and pathways of PFAS compounds have also been investigated at pilot-scale. Finally, a modified cycle of ECOSEDRA washing treatment has been proposed and investigated to improve PFAS removal from dredged sediments. This modification consisted in the addition of H₂O₂ during the final washing step of sediments.

During laboratory scale experiments, PFAS removal was investigated using sediments from Ancona port and sediments samples from Netherlands, which presented a much higher contamination level. Results showed that removal of PFAS from both the sediment matrices is mainly correlated with removal of organic material. The addition of H₂O₂ improved PFAS removal from the solid matrix. However, it was observed that washing under acid or alkaline condition or under oxidative conditions related to H₂O₂ addition may have favored degradation of some precursors and release of the short-chain PFBA in the liquid washing solution. Indeed, the most abundant compound detected in liquid fraction was PFBA in all the accomplished experimental tests. Particularly, the addition of H₂O₂ increased the presence of PFBA in the produced washing solutions.

PFAS removal by ECOSEDRA treatment performed at pilot scale were lower than those observed at laboratory scale. This fact was dependent on the operational conditions utilized for mixing and recirculating the sediments within the reactor, and on the system used for the addition of acid and alkaline solutions. Hence, the operation of the reactor at pilot-scale needs improvements.

Regarding the structure of this report, the first section of the document (**section 1**) gives an introduction of the topic by discussing environmental issues related to the PFAS presence in dredged sediments, and by providing an overview of available technologies for sediments treatment.

Section 2 describes the methodology used for the accomplishment of the work. Hence, here are described the working operations of ECOSEDRA plant as well as their simulation at laboratory scale. In addition, all analytical methods to measure PFAS or characterize sediments are reported.

In the third section (**section 3**) are reported and discussed all the results obtained by the experimental tests accomplished at laboratory scale and at demo scale. All obtained results have been critically compared and discussed.

The conclusions of the investigation are reported in **section 4**.

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List of Abbreviations

CE = Circular Economy
DOM = dissolved organic matter
EEM = Excitation Emission Matrix
EER= European Waste Catalogue
EIS = Extracted Internal Standard
EQS = Environmental Quality Standard
LC-MS/MS = Liquid Chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry
LOI = Loss on Ignition
LOQ = Limit of Quantification
MB = Method Blanks
MRM = multiple reaction monitoring
PFAAs = Perfluoroalkyl acid
PFAS = Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFC = Perfluorinated compound
PFCA = Perfluorocarboxylate
PFSA = Perfluorosulfonate
PM = Persistent Mobile
RB = Reagent Blanks
RT = retention time
TRL = Technology readiness level
XRD = X-ray diffraction
XRF = X-ray fluorescence

List of Monitored PFAS Compounds

PFAS list	Name	CAS-NUMBER
EtFOSAA	N-Ethyl perfluorooctane sulfonamido acetic acid	1336-61-4 or 2991-50-6
HFPO-DA (= GenX)	hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid /perfluoro-2-propoxypropanoic acid	13252-13-6
MeFOSAA	N-Methyl perfluorooctane sulfonamido acetic acid	2355-31-9
NADONA	4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoic acid	958445-44-8
PFBA	perfluorobutanoic acid	375-22-4
PFBS	Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid	375-73-5 or 59933-66-3
PFDA	perfluorodecanoic acid	335-76-2
PFDoDA	perfluorododecanoic acid	307-55-1
PFDoDS	perfluorododecane sulfonic acid	79780-39-5
PFDS	perfluorodecane sulfonic acid	335-77-3
PFHpA	perfluoroheptanoic acid	375-85-9
PFHpS	perfluoroheptane acid	375-92-8
PFHxA	perfluorohexanoic acid	307-24-4
PFHxS	perfluorohexane sulfonic acid	355-46-4
PFNA	acid perfluorononanoique	375-95-1
PFNS	Perfluorononane sulfonic acid	68259-12-1
PFOA	perfluorooctanoic acid	335-67-1
PFOS	perfluorooctane sulfonic acid	1763-23-1
PFOSA	Perfluorooctane sulfonamide	754-91-6
PFPeA	perfluoropentanoic acid	2706-90-3
PFPeS	perfluoropentane sulfonic acid	2706-91-4
PFTeDA	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	376-06-7
PFTrDA	acid perfluorotridecanoique	72629-94-8
PFTrDS	Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid	174675-49-1
PFUnDA	perfluoroundecanoic acid	2058-94-8
PFUnDS	perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid	749786-16-1
4:2 FTSA	4:2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	757124-72-4
6:2 FTSA	6:2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	27619-97-2
8:2 FTSA	8:2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid	39108-34-4
C604	Acetic acid, 2,2-difluoro-2-[[2,2,4,5-tetrafluoro-5-(trifluoromethoxy)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl]oxy]-, ammonium salt (1:1)	1190931-27-1

1. Introduction

1.1. Environmental issues related to the PFAS presence in dredged sediments

PFAS are used in a wide variety of products and industries such as electronics manufacturing, metal plating, textiles, lubricants, cookware, firefighting foams, carpeting, and food packaging materials (Kempisty&Racz, 2021). Due to the global spread of PFAS, a new planetary boundary for PFAS has been exceeded, with the irreversibility to PFAS exposure (Cousins et al., 2022). These chemicals have been found worldwide, even in the North Pole (Bossi et al., 2005). Transportation and spread of PFAS throughout the environment mean that all existing matrices are affected (Kempisty&Racz, 2021). Particularly, sediments and oceans have resulted to be a significant sink for PFAS compounds, which are released in the environment by human activities (Yamashita et al., 2008).

Sediments categorized as hazardous by current regulations are only allowed to be either directly disposed in landfills for hazardous wastes or to be treated to reduce their potential toxicity to admissible levels. Considering the high amounts of dredged sediments produced worldwide, around 300 million of m³ per year only in Europe (Snellings et al., 2016), and the increasing legal requirements in terms of sediment management, the “no action” scenario as well as conventional practices for contaminated sediments, such as direct disposal in confined facilities, are no longer feasible economically, environmentally, and socially (Barjoveanu et al., 2018; Mehdizadeh et al., 2021; Pal and Hogland, 2022; Pellenz et al., 2020). Sediment dredging therefore represents a challenge for port authorities (Loudini et al., 2020), which are usually open to a new approach of sediment management that could help them to cope with this environmental problem. In this respect, increasing number of studies are trying to apply Circular Economy (CE) principles to the dredged sediment management sector.

However, the reuse of treated sediments for useful application, such as road construction, may represent an environmental threat due to the presence contaminants like PFAS in the sediment. To provide answer to this question, within PROMISCES project, we have planned different experimental activities to evaluate the fate of PFAS during dredged sediments treatment.

1.2. Literature analysis on PFAS presence in dredged sediments

In a study conducted in South Carolina, sediment samples were collected from 36 sites around the Charleston Harbor and its tributaries, the Ashley and Cooper Rivers. Among the 11 compounds measured in sediments, PFOS, PFDA, and PFOA were those detected with high frequency and concentrations, which ranged from 0.22 µg/kg d.w. (dry weight) to 19.21 µg/kg d.w.. On the other side, the average total PFAS concentrations was 3.72 µg/kg d.w. (White et al., 2015). Ahmadireskety et al., (2021) monitored in their study in Florida 51 different PFAS components. Among the monitored compounds, only 28 were detected in sediments, which included 13 PFCAs, 6 PFSA, and 7 precursors. The predominant PFAS detected in sea sediments were PFOS and PFBA. Short-chain PFCAs (C < 7) were dominant in 68% of the monitored sites, while long-chain PFAAs (PFSA with C ≥ 6 and PFCA with C ≥ 7) were dominant in the remaining 32% of sites (Ahmadireskety et al., 2021). In another study conducted in Canada by Yeung et al., (2013), PFOS, PFHxS, and FOSA were detected in sediments with a frequency of 100, 92, and 65%, respectively. The measured concentrations ranged from 1.1 to 72.8 µg/kg. On the contrary, no detectable PFDS and PFBS concentrations were found. Measured concentrations of PFSA, including FOSA, comprised >65% of the total PFAS in the samples, and over 60% of the PFSA was PFOS. Long-chain PFCAs were a major proportion (over 80%) of total

PFCAs (Yeung et al., 2013). Labadie and Chevreuil (2011) reported that the highest contribution in sediments from river was that of PFOS (56.5%), followed by long-chain carboxylic acids: PFDoA (20.5%), PFTeA (10.2%) and PFDA (3.6%). The PFOA was detected, but below the analytical quantification limit (Labadie and Chevreuil, 2011).

In Table 1 is reported a summary of observed concentrations of PFAS in sediments according to the research studies mentioned above. PFAS compounds were detected in sediments sampled from rivers, marine environments, and lakes from different countries of the World.

Table 1: PFAS detected in sediments from different environments, and observed concentrations as sum of PFAS (Σ PFAS)

REFERENCE	MATRIX	Detected PFAS	Σ PFAS (ug/kg)
(White et al., 2015)	Estuarine sediments	PFBS, PFxS, PFDS and PFOS	0.22 – 19.21
(Ahmadireskety et al., 2021)	Estuarine sediments	PFCA, PFSA, FTCA, n:2 FTS, FASA, FTUCA, PFPi, diPAP, precursors and others	0.022 – 3.89
(Yeung et al., 2013)	Sediments from Lake	PFDS, PFOS, PFHxS, PFBS, FOSA, PFxSA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFDoDA, PFUnDA, PFBA, PFHpA, PFPeA	1.1 – 72.8
(Labadie and Chevreuil, 2011)	Sediments from river	PFPA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDoA, PFTrA, PFTeA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS and PFDS	8.4
(Lam et al., 2014)	Sediments from river and lakes	PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDoA, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS	0.03-1.09
(Wang et al., 2013)	Sediments from marine environments	PFCAs, PFSAs, PFOA, PDFA, PFUDA, PFTrDA, PFOS, precursors (e.g., FOSAA).	0.11-0.48

1.3. Overview of available technologies for sediments/soils treatment

Conventional treatments of dredged sediments aim at reducing the toxicity of the material in order to dispose it in landfill for inert material, avoiding the landfilling of hazardous sediments, which is extremely expensive. The landfill costs for inert sediments are around 27 USD/t. However, these costs can increase up to 67–80 USD/t, when wastes are toxic (Norén et al., 2020). Table 2 reports an overview of conventional treatments for dredged sediments, which include physical operations, chemical, thermal, and biological treatments (Crocetti et al., 2022). However, these treatments are generally applied to remove contaminants such as hydrocarbons and heavy metals. On the other side, only few data are available about the fate of PFAS during sediments treatment. Bolan et al., (2022) published a review about remediation of PFAS in contaminated soils. These authors examined mobilization (e.g., soil washing, soil flushing), immobilization (e.g., addition of activated carbons, solidification/stabilization) and destruction techniques (e.g., thermal treatment) for poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in soils. Most of the studies available, have been focused on PFOS and PFOA removal, even though many other PFAS may be present in the contaminated soils. Furthermore, these studies have been generally accomplished at laboratory scale, while data related to PFAS presence in sediments treated at full-scale plants are very scarce.

Mobilization techniques are found to be effective for PFAS removals from soil after addition of proper mobilization amendments (often consisting in toxic solutions and solvent) (Table 3). However, further treatments will be later required to destroy desorbed PFAS, which will be contained in the washing solution. Immobilization is also an effective technology for reducing the mobility of Persistent Mobile (PM) substances. Although PFAS compounds become less mobile and bioavailable, their overall mass in soils is unaltered. Immobilized PFAS compounds may become solubilized and bioavailable after several years due to aging and breakdown.

Table 2: Conventional treatment for dredged sediments (Crocetti et al., 2022)

Treatment		Goal of the process	Target Wastes	Performance	Costs
Physical operations	Mechanical separation	To divide sediments in sand, silt and clay fractions	Sediment	Generally high performance	3–11 € (2007) m ⁻³
	Washing (acid)	To reduce pollutant and salt concentration in sediments	Metals, salts	Performance is dependent on operational conditions parameters, such as used reagent, dosage, contact time, temperature, etc..	40–73 € (2009)·m ⁻³
Chemical treatment	Chemical oxidation	To degrade pollutants into non-hazardous compounds	Organic pollutants	Performance is dependent on the chemical reagent, type of pollutant and water content. Poor metal removal.	Depending on conditions
	Solidification/ Stabilisation	To immobilise pollutants	Metals	Good performance with As, Pb, Cr(VI), Hg, Cd, Cu, Zn. Poor performance with high content of organics, salts and with certain metals.	10 – 41 € (2007)·m ⁻³
Thermal treatment	Thermal desorption	To separate Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) sediments	Organic pollutants	Highly effective for VOCs (T = 450–500 °C) and for some metals (T = 800 °C).	50 – 70 € (2007)·t ⁻¹
	Thermal oxidation	To degrade organic pollutants		High performance if temperature is adequate	50 – 70 € (2007)·t ⁻¹
	Thermal immobilisation	To immobilise metals	Metals	Performance depends on the sediment characteristics. Generally, this treatment is more effective than chemical Solidification/ Stabilisation	50 – 70 € (2007)·t ⁻¹
	Vitrification	To destroy and/or immobilise pollutants	Metals	Very effective.	Costs are highly variable with operating conditions
Biological processes	-	To degrade pollutants by microbial activity	Biodegradable organic pollutants	Low, often undetectable, degradation rates	

Table 3: Mobilization of PFAS in contaminated soils (Bolan et al., 2022)

Added amendments for PFAS mobilization	PFAS compounds	Observations	Reference
0.01 mol/L CaCl ₂ and 0.03 g of NaN ₃	PFOA, PFBS and PFOS	Desorption yields of PFOA, PFBS and PFOS were 15-19%, 18-27% and <4%, respectively	Milinic et al., (2016)
Acetic acid	Perfluorocarboxylates (PFCAs) and perfluorosulfonates (PFSAs)	Desorption experiments indicated desorption became difficult as the chain length increased, and PFSAs were harder to be desorbed than the corresponding PFCAs	Zhao et al., (2012)
Rainwater	PFOA and PFOS	Of the 360 g of PFOA and 367.5 g of PFOS applied to the soil, loss from the soil plot through leachate amounted to 3.12% for PFOA and 0.013% for PFOS. Short-chain PFASs and PFOA pass through the soil much more quickly than PFOS	Stahl et al., (2013)
Water	perfluorinated compounds (PFCs)	The short chain PFC could pass through the soil without retention and were likely to be carried away easily with surface runoff	Gillich et al., (2012)
Cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), and an anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl-benzene sulfonate (SDBS)	PFOS	While CTAB remarkably enhanced the sorption of PFOS on the sediment, SDBS increased the desorption of PFOS	Pan et al., (2009)
Oxalate and root exudates	PFOS	Oxalate increased PFOS desorption by 1.43- to 17.14-fold, effects of root exudates were similar to those of oxalate	Tang et al., (2017)
Methanol with ammonium acetate	86 PFASs	Methanol with hydrochloric acid provided excellent recoveries for most cationic and zwitterionic PFASs	Munoz et al., (2018)
100 mM of CaCl ₂	6 PFCs	The desorption was lower than Adsorption, the soil matrix may act as a protective barrier towards extensive groundwater contamination	Enevoldsen and Juhler (2010)
Supercritical carbon dioxide (Sc-CO ₂)	PFOS and PFOA	The extraction efficiencies (with double extractions) were approximately 77%-100% for PFOA and 59%-80% for PFOS	Chen et al., (2012b)
Ethanol	PFOS	The regeneration percent of PFOS from spent activated carbon was 84% after 0.5 h and 98% after 23 h using 50% ethanol solution at 45 °C	Deng et al., (2015)

Added amendments for PFAS mobilization	PFAS compounds	Observations	Reference
Ethanol and NaCl in methanol solution	PFCAs	50% ethanol at 45 °C and 1% NaCl in 70% methanol solution were suitable for the desorption of PFCAs from the bamboo-derived activated carbon and resin IRA67, respectively	Du et al., (2015)
Ethyl acetate—dimethylformamide and methanol—phosphoric acid	PAEO, PFOS and PFOA	The sequential use of ethyl acetate—dimethylformamide and methanol—phosphoric acid in combination with pressurized liquid extraction resulted in exhaustive extraction of fluorinated anionic and non-ionic surfactants in sewage sludge	Schröder (2003)
Nonaqueous phase liquid (NAPL), anionic surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and n,n-dimethyldodecylamine n-oxide (AO)	perfluoroalkyl acid (PFAAs)	NAPL, SDS and AO led to decrease in the sorption of PFOS at lower PFOS concentrations (1 µg/L)	Guelfo and Higgins (2013)

1.4. Objectives of research activities

Dredged sediments are characterized by the presence of high proportions of silt and clay fractions, and they tend to adsorb and accumulate potential toxic pollutants such as heavy metals and organic contaminants (e.g., hydrocarbons). Hence, they are often classified as hazardous wastes according to national regulations. Physical operations and/or chemical, thermal, and biological processes are needed to reduce pollutants content in sediments as well as the risk of pollutants resuspensions and spreading into the environment.

Conventional technologies for treating dredged sediments are significantly expensive. However, with the increasing people's awareness in environmental issues and the more restrictive regulations worldwide that hinder the disposal of sediments in landfills, more sustainable and circular approaches for the management of dredged sediments are becoming appealing.

In this context, the Italian Project ECOSEDRA was designed with the purpose of creating and validating at demonstrative scale (TRL > 7) an innovative technological solution for the eco-sustainable management of sediments from port dredging operations. Particularly, within ECOSEDRA project, a prototype sediment treatment plant fed with 25-50 kg/h of dredged sludge from Ancona Sea port has been implemented to produce construction materials for reuse in road embankments. ECOSEDRA treatment is based on mechanical treatments to divide sediments in coarse and fine fractions. Then, fine fractions are cleaned by using different washing solutions. The project proposal aims to implement the principles of circular economy during sediments management with the purpose to reach energy minimization, carbon footprint and other environmental impacts reduction.

Since, in the case of sediment granulometric separation and sediment fraction washing, there are limited information regarding the mass flow of PFAS compounds, research activities in PROMISCES project aimed at investigating the fate of PFAS compounds during the pre-treatments as well as the washing treatments of marine sediments during the ECOSEDRA treatments.

Fate and mass flow analysis of PFAS compounds during ECOSEDRA treatments has been investigated at laboratory and pilot scale. Furthermore, a modification of ECOSEDRA treatment cycle has been proposed and tested to increase the removal of PFAS from treated dredged sediments.

2. Methodology

2.1. Tested raw dredged sediments

The dredged sediments analyzed and used to study PFAS removals during ECOSEDRA treatments are from the harbor of Ancona in Italy, and from a depot of fluvial sediments in the Netherlands.

Regarding the dredged sediments of Ancona, these were collected in both the reclaimed tank and docks located in the Harbor of Ancona (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Points of collection of the dredged sediments from Italy (Ancona).

The sediments from Netherlands are fluvial sediments which comes from a depot, which is an artificial island located in a lake. Providers of the contaminated sediments asked to keep anonymous the sampling area, which is impacted by a significant PFAS contamination according to a declaration of the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (RWS).

2.2. ECOSEDRA pilot plant

ECOSSEDRA pilot plant is a technological solution (TRL>7) for the treatment and the recovery of dredged sediments (classified as waste EER 170506). The pilot plant is installed in Senigallia (Ancona, Italy) and the recovered material will be tested for the realization of road embankment. The main objectives of ECOSEDRA washing treatments are:

1. To treat the sediments according to End of Waste criteria by respecting the limits of the column B of the attachment 5 at the title V of the fourth part of the Italian Legislative Decree 152/2006, and the limits of the attachment 3 of the Decree of the Ministry of the Environment of the 5th of February 1998
2. To obtain a recovered material which respects the necessary requisites for land classification in the A7-5 group (UNI 11531-1).

ECOSSEDRA pilot plant (Figure 2) is composed by one line of dredged sediments treatment, with a capacity of 200 kg/d. The process units of the plant are (Figure 3):

- Storage of the dredged sediments
- Shredding and sieving units to separate fine fractions from course materials
- Section for the mixing and homogenization of sieved fine material
- Storage section of the demineralized water
- Washing section for the treatment of fine fractions of sediments
- Storage section of the waste washing-water solutions
- Storage and dosage section of the acid/base reagents for the pH correction of the washing water
- Dewatering section composed by dehydration unit and drying sections (i.e., electric dryer) of the sieved and washed material (i.e., plate filter press)

Figure 2. ECOSEDRA treatment plant.

Figure 3. Schematic flow diagram of ECOSEDRA treatment plant.

Below is reported a detailed description of the treatment units included in ECOSEDRA pilot plant.

Description of the units

Package unit of shredding and sieving

The settled dredged sediments in the reclaimed tank are taken with an excavator with waterproof bucket and stored at the storage tank (L = 7.8 m; W = 2.5 m; H = 2.98 m; capacity = 15 ton), covered with a waterproof sheet. The package unit of shredding and sieving (P = 25 kW; L = 8 m; W = 4 m) is manually loaded with about 200 kg/d of dredged sediments. The package unit comprises:

- N. 1 hammer mill to shred the material.
- N. 1 wet sieve for the removal of the parts with a diameter greater than 2 mm.
- N. 1 stripper tape for transporting the material exiting from the sieve mill; the parts which do not pass through the sieve form the overkill.
- N. 1 stripper tape that recirculates the overkill in the hammer mill for a further shredding process; the recirculation is repeated enough times to minimize the coarse fraction production.

The remaining overkill is manually transferred to a big bag (L = 0.9 m; W = 0.9 m; H = 1.2 m; capacity = 1 t).

Figure 4: Shredding and sieving units of the ECOSEDRA pilot plant

Mixing and homogenization section

The material passing through the sieve (underrated) is sent to the mixing and homogenization section ($V = 1 \text{ m}^3$; $D = 1.2 \text{ m}$; $H = 0.88 \text{ m}$) by gravity. This section comprises a weighing hopper and a vertical mixer ($\text{rpm} = 120$; $P = 1.1 \text{ kW}$). The material is homogenized with a known amount of demineralized water which comes from the package unit of reverse osmosis, and it is sent to the reactor through a horizontal centrifugal pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 2 \text{ bar}$; $P = 2.2 \text{ kW}$). In order to enhance the material homogenization, a progressive cavity pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 1 \text{ bar}$; $P = 0.37 \text{ kW}$) operates the recirculation of the solution in the reactor. During the recirculation phase, part of the solution material/water is sent to the washing reactor.

Figure 5: Mixing section

Washing section

The washing section (Figure 6) aims at washing away the material coming from the mixing and homogenization reactor in a washing tank ($V = 7 \text{ m}^3$; $D = 1.5 \text{ m}$; $H_1 = 3.2 \text{ m}$; $H_2 = 0.75 \text{ m}$), which comprises a weighing hopper and a vertical mixer (rpm = 0-120; $P = 1.5 \text{ kW}$). The wash cycle is composed of 3 phases:

1. First phase of washing with demineralized water through a fast mixing for 5 minutes.
2. Second phase of low mixing for 10 minutes.
3. Third phase of separation of the sludge from the water for about 20-30 minutes.

A horizontal centrifugal pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 2 \text{ bar}$; $P = 2.2 \text{ kW}$) operates the sludge recirculation to the head of the reactor. The following reagents are dosed at the pump delivery:

- Acid solution (H_3PO_4), or alkaline solution (NaOH), dosed by the respective dosage pumps ($Q_{\text{max}} = 50 \text{ L/h}$; $H = 4 \text{ bar}$; $P = 0.37 \text{ kW}$). The flowrate of the pump is regulated through a pH analyzer.

The washing process is performed with the same demineralized water mentioned for the mixing and homogenization section, delivered with the same pump. A centrifuge pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 3 \text{ bar}$; $P = 3 \text{ kW}$) located at the exit of the water line operates the recirculation of the washing water. The residual water is collected in an intermediate accumulation tank for waste solutions ($V = 20 \text{ m}^3$; $H = 4 \text{ m}$; $D = 2.5 \text{ m}$).

Figure 6: Washing section

Package unit of reverse osmosis

The package unit of reverse osmosis allows the demineralization of the tap water. The demineralized water produced is then collected in a storage tank ($V = 20 \text{ m}^3$; $H = 5.47 \text{ m}$; $D = 2.3 \text{ m}$). The concentrate resulting from the osmosis process is stored in a separated tank as a waste.

Figure 7: Reverse Osmosis Unit

Dehydration unit (plate filter press) and drying unit

The sludge settled at the bottom of the washing reactor is transferred to the intermediate accumulation tank ($V = 3 \text{ m}^3$; $H = 2.98 \text{ m}$; $D = 1.4 \text{ m}$) through a progressive cavity pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 2 \text{ bar}$; $P = 2.2 \text{ kW}$). The package unit of plate filter press ($P = 6 \text{ kW}$) comprises 60 plates $500 \times 500 \text{ mm}$, and it is fed with the sludge coming from the intermediate accumulation tank through another progressive cavity pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 14 \text{ bar}$; $P = 3 \text{ kW}$). Once reached the complete dewater of the sludge, the plate pack is opened, and the dewatered sludge is collected in the underlying tank ($L = 7.8 \text{ m}$; $W = 2.5 \text{ m}$; $h = 2.02 \text{ m}$; capacity = 15 ton). From there, the dewatered sludge is manually loaded to the thermal drying unit (electrical dryer) (Figure 8). The water resulting from the plate filter press process is sent by gravity to the collecting cockpit, which contains a submersible pump ($Q_{\text{max}} = 36 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 1.45 \text{ bar}$; $P = 1.5 \text{ kW}$) that sends the residual water from the sludge dewatering and drying sections to the storage tank for liquid waste solutions.

The sludge is finally desiccated by the electrical dryer. Once a drying cycle is finished, the dry sludge is manually discharged in the storage tank ($L = 7.8 \text{ m}$; $W = 2.5 \text{ m}$; $H = 2.98 \text{ m}$; capacity = 15 t).

Figure 8: Filter press for sediments dewatering on the left and drying unit on the right

2.2.1 Simulation of ECOSEDRA treatment at laboratory scale

The process performed by ECOSEDRA pilot plant was reproduced at laboratory scale. A schematic representation of the lab-scale treatments is given in Figure 9.

Figure 9. ECOSEDRA treatment plant at laboratory scale.

The procedure consists basically of 3 washing steps (acid washing, basic washing and final washing with demineralized water) with some pretreatments. These different steps to treat sediments were carried out as described below:

- At the beginning of the process, the sample was mixed with water ($m/v = 1 \text{ kg}/1 \text{ L}$) and pre-treated through shredding and sieving (4 mm) to remove the coarse material.
- After the pre-treatments, the acid washing was performed by putting the sample in a tank with water ($m/v = 1 \text{ kg}/20 \text{ L}$) and phosphoric acid 75% (0.5 L for 1 m^3 of water) and mixing for 30 minutes (Figure 10). After that, the mixing was stopped and the solution settled for one night.
- After completion of the settling phase, the acid solution was removed and replaced with water ($m/v = 1 \text{ kg}/20 \text{ L}$) and NaOH 30% (1 L for 1 m^3 of water) for proceeding with the basic washing. Again, the sample was mixed for 30 minutes and then settled for one night.
- The last step was the washing with demineralized water ($m/v = 1 \text{ kg}/20 \text{ L}$), which replaced the alkaline solution. The sample was mixed for 30 minutes and then settled.

Figure 10: (a) Mixing (b) Sedimentation phases during the sediment washing performed at laboratory scale

2.2.2 Alternative procedure for sediments washing

As described in the following chapters, ECOSEDRA washing treatments performed a partial removal of PFAS from raw dredged sediments. Therefore, alternative washing procedures, including chemical oxidation techniques, have been tested at laboratory scale to increase the efficiency of PFAS removal during sediments washing. For this scope, hydrogen peroxide was used as amendment of the washing solution. Experimental tests were performed as described below to evaluate the suitable concentration of H_2O_2 to add to the washing solution as described below:

- At the beginning of the process, the sample was mixed with water ($m/v = 1\text{kg}/1\text{L}$) and pre-treated through shredding and sieving (4 mm) to remove the coarse material.
- After the pre-treatments, sediments were washed with a mix of hydrogen peroxide and water ($m/v = 1\text{kg}/20\text{L}$) in the reactor for 30 minutes. After that, the mixing was stopped, and the sediment settled for one night.

Three H_2O_2 dosages were tested during these trials: 2 mmol, 4 mmol and 8 mmol of hydrogen peroxide (30 % v/v) per grams of dry sediments to identify the most effective dosage for the removal of PFAS.

Finally, according to the obtained results, the ECOSEDRA washing procedure was modified by adding 2 mmol H_2O_2/g to the final washing step (washing with demineralized water) to increase the removal of PFAS from dredged sediments.

Hydrogen peroxide was selected as amendment of the washing solution, since H_2O_2 is a well know radical promoter that can be still utilized for the removal of PFAS from the produced washing solution. Indeed, PROMISCES project in subtask 3.2.2 will test advanced oxidation processes (i.e., ultrasonic cavitation technology) to destroy PFAS in the liquid solution obtained after sediment washing. Particularly, the presence of H_2O_2 in the solution can increase the production of hydroxyl radicals during the treatments. Results of this study will be reported in Deliverable D3.4 “Assessing the treatment performance of PFAS degradation/ immobilization in the liquid and solid sediment fractions: a toxicity risk assessment” (M36).

2.3. Analytical methods

2.3.1 Target PFAS analysis in sediments and washing waters

Target PFAS in sediments and washing water were analysed following the method described in WP1 (reported in D1.1), which developed a cost-effective testing method for PFAS analysis in complex matrices. The test method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators. The developed procedure and the obtained performance ensure robustness, reliability, and fast turnaround time, with low material costs, high throughput (more than 20 samples per day) and meet the needs for continuous PFAS control and monitoring in complex matrices. Particularly, the repeatability of the obtained analytical results was verified on N.10 aliquots of 1 g each taken from actual sediment sample. Standard deviation of replicates (RSD) was <20% for the identified PFAS.

Samples are prepared using an appropriate sample preparation method (e.g., solvent dilution or extraction) to determinate n. 30 analytes of the perfluoroalkyl family of substances from environmental matrices of interest, liquid or solid. The laboratory set the LOQ values starting from lowest point on the calibration curve:

- 0.050 µg/kg on the sediment matrix;
- 0.015 µg/L on the washing water, deemed free of concentrated interfering substances.

Table 4: Analysed target PFAS and LOQ

30 target PFAS	PFDA, PFHpA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA, PFOS, PFDoDA, PFDoDS, PFDS, PFHpS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFTTrDA, PFTeDA, PFUnDA, PFBA, PFBS, 4:2 FTSA, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, NADONA, EtFOSAA, PFOSA, MeFOSAA, PFNS, PFPeS, PFTTrDS, PFUnDS, HFPO-DA (= GenX), C6O4
LOQ wastewater liquid	15 ng/L
LOQ solids	50 ng/kg

Before analytical measurements, sediments were dried at 40°C to remove humidity. Then, it was decided to apply a solid-liquid extraction procedure to extract PFAS from the solid matrix (sediments), using 10 mL of Methanol and sonicating at room temperature for 30 minutes, then the samples are centrifuged to separate suspended solids from the liquid phase, after that the extraction solvent is ready for instrumental analysis. The extract from sediment is concentrated at 1 mL by using a gentle stream of nitrogen gas. Two Extracted Internal Standard (EIS) are also added to monitor the analytical process.

Permeate and washing waters are directly prepared in the glass sampling container and then transferred into a vial, ready to be analyzed, in order not to lose PFAS adhered to the container wall.

All sample concentrations are determined by isotope dilution, according to the project-specific requirements, using isotopically labeled compounds added to the samples before injection. All the solutions prepared during the analysis must necessarily contain at least 30% of Methanol to keep under control filming process on the walls of the containers. Analysis is conducted by LC-MS/MS in the multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) and negative ionization mode.

The target compounds are qualitatively identified in samples by comparing retention times (RTs) to RTs of isotopically labeled surrogates in the same samples or to RTs of target analytes in standards, as applicable, and by comparing product ion ratios to those in standards development. Qualitatively

identified target compounds are then quantified based on their primary product ion responses utilizing NIS.

Possible interferents can be caused by the matrix, solvents, reagents, analytical standards and by glassware contamination. Method Blanks (MB) and Reagent Blanks (RB) are prepared and analyzed with all samples and are used to demonstrate that laboratory supplies, preparation, and analysis steps, do not introduce interferences or PFAS artifacts at levels that would prevent the proper identification and integration of target analytes or bias quantitation, especially near the Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) or any project-specific concentration levels of interest. Careful selection of reagents and consumables is necessary because even low levels of PFAS contamination may alter the precision and bias of the method; background introduced by these materials (and variability thereof) is cumulative.

2.3.2 Laboratory techniques for sediments characterization

The physical characterization was obtained by granulometric analysis, which was conducted using Ancona and Netherlands sediments and according to the ASTM D7928-21 methodology, for the determination of distribution size of fine-grained sediments (<75 μm), and following the ASTM D6913-04, for the particle-distribution of sediments from 75 μm to 75 mm. Moreover, total solid (TS%) and volatile solids (TVS%) in the solid matrix as well as the pH and DOC in the washing waters were measured according to standard laboratory procedures (APHA, 2012).

On the other side, the point of zero charge (pzc), defined as the pH at which the number of negatively and positively charged sites on the surface of the sediments are equal (net charge on surface = 0) was experimentally determined by calculating the slurry pH (Tan et al., 2008). This test was accomplished for both treated and raw sediments, and it is useful to evaluate electrostatic attractions between sediments and monitored PFAS.

In addition to these tests, major element sediment composition was determined by XRF and loss on ignition (LOI) using methods described in the literature (Boyle, 2000). Rietveld-based XRD quantification was also used to quantify weight percentage of inorganic elements in sediments (Ruan and Ward, 2002). These latter tests were also accomplished for treated and untreated sediments collected in Ancona (Italy) and the Netherlands.

2.3.3 Characterization of organic matter released in the washing solutions

Characterization of organic material released in the washing solution was accomplished using spectroscopic measurements, such UV absorbance and fluorescence spectroscopy.

Ultraviolet light absorbance was analyzed using a Shimadzu UV-1900i spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan). Absorbance spectra were measured from 200 to 800 nm at 1 nm intervals in a 1 cm quartz cuvette with Milli-Q water used as a blank.

Fluorescence Excitation Emission Matrices (EEMs) were collected using a Shimadzu RF-6000 fluorescence spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan) with the scanning range from excitation wavelength 220 nm–450 nm at an interval of 5 nm and emission wavelength from 250 nm to 580 nm at the interval of 1 nm. Excitation and emission slit widths were both set at 5 nm. The Raman scatter effect was minimized by subtracting EEMs of pure Milli-Q water from the sample EEMs; any negative intensity values produced by this subtraction were converted to zero values. Then, the emission intensity data were normalized to the Raman peak area of an emission wavelengths scan of Milli-Q water samples collected at the interval of 1 nm and related to an excitation wavelength of 350 nm to

produce fluorescence intensities in Raman unit. Non-trilinear data related to the Rayleigh scattering were eliminated. Inner filter effect correction was accomplished according to the methodology proposed by Demchenko (2009).

Five fluorescence peaks were selected across an EEM as representative indices of different dissolved organic matter (DOM) components by peak-picking method (Sgroi et al., 2020). The excitation/emission wavelength positions of the selected fluorescence peaks are reported in Table 5 and Figure 11.

Table 5: Interpretations of fluorescence peaks

Fluorescence peak	Description	Excitation wavelength (nm)	Emission wavelength (nm)
I1	Aromatic protein, tyrosine-like fluorescence	225	290
I2	Aromatic protein, tryptophan-like fluorescence	225	340
I3	Fulvic-like and humic-like fluorescence	245	440
I4	Microbial byproducts, proteins, biopolymers, and tryptophan-like fluorescence	275	345
I5	Humic-like fluorescence	345	440

Figure 11: Fluorescence spectrum example

All liquid samples were filtered at 0.45 μm glass filter (Whatman) before spectroscopic measurements.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Sediments characterization

Sediments characterization, which was obtained by granulometric analysis, determination of total and volatile solids, and measurement of the point of zero charge, is reported in Table 6 for both sediments collected at Ancona port (Italy) and in the Netherlands.

Table 6: Characterization of sediments from Ancona Port and Netherlands

Feature	Grain size (mm)	Ancona port	Netherlands sediments
Sand (%)	0.075 – 4.75	7	42
Silt (%)	0.002 – 0.075	56	45
Clay (%)	<0.002	37	13
%TVS/TS	-	9.2	11.1
point of zero charge of raw sediments	-	8.3	7.9
point of zero charge of treated sediments	-	8.5	8.1

By the results of the granulometric analysis, it is important to observe that Ancona sediments have a significantly higher content of material with size lower than 0.002 mm (clay) compared to the sediments from Netherlands. On the contrary, the sediments from the Netherlands have a higher content of sand (i.e., particle between 0.075 – 4.75 mm). Non-important differences can be observed in terms of content of volatile solids or point of zero charge between the two kind sediments. Furthermore, the point of zero charge changed very slightly after the washing treatment for both kind of sediments (Table 6). Additional characterization features for the two sediments before and after the washing were obtained by XRF, LOI and XRD analyses, and are reported in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7: Major element sediment compositions determined by XRF and loss on ignition (LOI) (in weight percent). Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) values (n=3)

	Ancona sediment before washing		Ancona sediment after washing		Netherlands sediment before washing		Netherlands sediment after washing	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Na₂O	2.51	0.22	0.59	0.25	0.34	0.05	0.29	0.14
MgO	1.67	0.05	1.53	0.05	1.41	0.02	1.49	0.01
Al₂O₃	5.78	0.05	5.68	0.07	7.86	0.08	8.54	0.06
SiO₂	37.70	0.18	39.20	0.26	51.21	0.32	47.96	0.25
P₂O₅	0.11	0.00	0.32	0.02	1.00	0.01	1.28	0.03
K₂O	1.56	0.01	1.57	0.03	1.66	0.02	1.76	0.04
CaO	23.70	0.19	25.88	0.22	7.69	0.07	8.30	0.06
TiO₂	0.25	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.61	0.01	0.66	0.01
MnO	0.09	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.17	0.00
Fe₂O₃	2.69	0.02	2.54	0.02	5.73	0.06	6.31	0.05
LOI	23.92	-	22.36	-	22.34	-	23.25	-

Table 8: Rietveld-based XRD quantification results of the inorganic sediment samples in wt.% of the crystalline phase. Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) values (n=3)

	Ancona sediment before washing		Ancona sediment after washing		Netherlands sediment before washing		Netherlands sediment after washing	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Kaolinite	0.6	0.1	0.5	0.2	2.4	0.2	2.1	0.2
Calcite	38.4	0.1	41.4	0.2	15.4	0.1	16.6	0.1
Muscovite	11.3	0.2	8.3	0.2	13.2	0.3	17.6	0.2
Quartz	35.3	0.1	37.0	0.2	59.4	0.2	53.3	0.1
Halite	4.5	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Albite	7.1	0.2	10.0	0.2	5.5	0.2	5.6	0.2
Dolomite	2.7	0.1	2.8	0.1	4.1	0.1	4.8	0.1

The sediments from Ancona, in terms of content of oxide elements, have a prevalent content of silicon dioxide (38%) and calcium oxide (24%); while for the crystalline fraction, the XRD analysis shows a high content of calcite (39%) and quartz (36%). Regarding the riverine sediments from Netherlands, high presence of silicon dioxide (58%) was detected by XRF, while for the crystalline fraction, the sediments have a prevalent content of quartz (56%), calcite (16%), and muscovite (15%).

Both sediments from Ancona and Netherlands showed a LOI of around 22 – 24%, which did not change after the ECOSEDRA washing treatment. This loss may be due to the removal of organic matter and carbonates during the determination of the LOI.

Observed differences in mineral compositions for the two types of sediments are an important factor, since this information may be correlated with observed differences in the removal of PFAS and organic material from sediments during the washing treatment as discussed later in this work.

3.2. Transfer and conversion of PFAS during simulated ECOSEDRA treatment at laboratory scale

The Table 9 and Table 10 for the Ancona sediments and Netherlands sediments, respectively. Analytical measurements were repeated several times to obtain representative data.

Table 9: Presence of PFAS in raw Ancona sediments

Detected PFAS	Frequency	Average concentration (ng/kg)	Standard Deviation (ng/kg)	Min (ng/kg)	Max (ng/kg)
PFBA	11/11	247	99	90	380
PFBS	1/11	45	-	-	-
PFPeA	4/11	102	129	37	295
PFOA	7/11	66	42	40	160
PFOS	11/11	228	103	86	412

Table 10: Presence of PFAS in raw sediments from Netherlands (n = 5)

Detected PFAS	Frequency	Average concentration (ng/kg)	Standard Deviation (ng/kg)	Min (ng/kg)	Max (ng/kg)
PFBA	4/5	426	284	125	810
PFBS	3/5	92	38	55	130
PFHxA	1/5	100	-	-	-
PFHpA	1/5	60	-	-	-
PFHxS	3/5	80	52	20	110
PFOA	5/5	110	52	50	190
PFOS	5/5	1811	778	1200	2850
N-MeFOSAA	5/5	158	43	110	220
N-EtFOSAA	5/5	1594	542	720	2080
PFUdA	1/5	50	-	-	-
PFDS	3/5	70	17	60	90

It is possible to observe a significant variation in terms of concentration of detected PFAS between the different measurements. If PFAS are not homogeneously distributed in the bulk-solid matrix, extraction of PFAS from different samplings of the solid material can lead to very different measurements as observed in this work. In Ancona sediments, PFBA and PFOS were the compounds always detected in all collected samples. On the contrary, in the sediments from Netherlands have always been detected PFOA, PFOS, N-MeFOSAA and N-EtFOSAA.

To date, regulation of PFAS in soils or sediments is lacking worldwide. However, few countries have proposed/set limits for the presence of some PFAS in sediments and soils: the Netherlands set an upper limit of 3,7 µg/kg and 1.9 µg/kg for PFOS and PFOA, respectively, in sediment/silt/soil, above which materials cannot be re-used or disposed on land. Although no binding PFAS limits in soils exists in Italy, thresholds of 0.5 mg/kg in green areas and 5 mg/kg in industrial areas for PFOA in soil have been proposed by the National Health Care Institute (Istituto Superiore di Sanità – ISS).

In Ancona sediments, detected PFAS compounds included PFBA, PFBS, PFPeA, PFOA and PFOS. Concentrations of PFOA or PFOS found in the raw sediments from Ancona port were always below the regulatory limits set in Netherlands, which are more restrictive than thresholds suggested in Italy. On the contrary, the detected concentration of PFOS in the riverine sediments were higher than its regulatory limit in Netherland. Generally, observed concentrations of PFAS substances in sediments from Netherlands were higher than those observed in Ancona sediments.

Before starting experiments to evaluate PFAS removal during soil washing treatment, blank tests of the ECOSEDRA process were carried out in order to exclude possible release of PFAS compounds from the reactor used during the laboratory tests. The ECOSEDRA reactor was washed with acid, alkaline and water solutions by reproducing an ECOSEDRA test without sediments and no PFAS were found in the collected liquid matrixes. Therefore, possible contamination sources related to the utilized equipment were excluded.

ECOSSEDRA treatments were simulated twice for Ancona sediments and twice for the Dutch sediments in order to check the reproducibility of the tests and obtain reliable results. The removal efficiencies of PFAS during the treatment were calculated considering the concentration of PFAS in raw sediment and in the treated sediment as follows:

$$R (\%) = \frac{C_{Raw\ Sediment} - C_{Treated\ Sediment}}{C_{Raw\ Sediment}}$$

Table 11 and Table 12 report results obtained after ECOSEDRA treatments of Ancona sediments using two different sediment samples.

Table 11: First test of ECOSEDRA treatment with Ancona sediments

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	210	70	67%	<15	<15	<15
PFBS	45	50	0%	<15	<15	<15
PFOA	60	<50	100% (>17%)*	<15	<15	<15
PFOS	265	<50	100% (>81%)*	<15	<15	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	580	120	79%	<15	<15	<15

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 12: Second test of ECOSEDRA treatment with Ancona sediments

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	380	100	74%	99	23	9
PFPeA	295	30	90%	152	46	17
PFOA	55	<50	100% (>9%)*	<15	<15	<15
PFOS	295	<50	100% (>83%)*	15	<15	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	1025	130	87%	265	70	26

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

After ECOSEDRA treatment, the long-chain PFAS detected in Ancona sediments (PFOA and PFOS) have always been reduced at concentration below the LOQ. Hence, these PFAS were not detected in the treated sediments during both the accomplished experimental tests. On the contrary, the short-chain PFBA, PFBS and PFPeA were still detected in the cleaned sediments. In addition, only short-chain compounds, except PFOS at very low concentration (15 ng/L), were detected in the liquid solutions, but only during the second test (Table 12). Regarding short-chain PFAS, their highest concentration was observed in the acidic solution, which is the first solution used in ECOSEDRA treatment, whereas decreasing concentrations were observed in the alkaline and neutral solutions. No long-chain PFAS (except PFOS in the second trial) were observed in the liquid fraction, probably, due to dilution effect that reduced their final concentration below the analytical LOQ for liquid samples (15 ng/L). Indeed, it is needed to observe that 20 L for each of the acid, alkaline and neutral solutions have been used to wash 1 kg of sediments. Overall, mass balance calculations between PFAS measured in the solid samples and in the liquid samples do not lead to comparable results. Discrepancy in the mass balance between liquid and solid fractions can be explained by two different factors: i) heterogeneous distribution of PFAS in solids, whose particle size characteristics are quite uneven as observed in Table 6 and ii) presence of precursors. Particularly, only few grams of samples are utilized for analysis, or the 1 kg of sediments used for the experimental tests cannot be representative of all the sediments stored in the Ancona ports. On the other side, degradation of PFAS precursors under acidic or alkaline conditions may have resulted in further release of short-chain compounds making impossible to perform mass balance calculation based on target screening of 30 PFAS components. This fact is also reported by previous studies, even though in different contexts (Bolan et al., 2022; Weidemann et al., 2022).

Release of organic material during the three washing steps was monitored by fluorescence analysis and measurement of DOC concentrations. Most of the organic material was released during the acid washing step, whereas decreasing amount of organic matter concentration was measured in the liquid solutions produced during the alkaline and neutral washing steps (Figure 12 and Figure 13). This observation is in agreement with the trend of observed release of PFAS compounds during the ECOSEDRA washing steps. Probably, PFAS compounds are bound to organic material present in sediments and released together during the soil washing treatment.

Figure 12: Dissolved organic matter (DOC) concentration and fluorescence spectra of liquid samples collected during the first ECOSEDRA treatment trial with Ancona sediments (left: acid washing, centre: alkaline washing, right: water washing)

Figure 13: Fluorescence spectra of liquid samples collected during the second ECOSEDRA treatment trial with Ancona sediments (left: acid washing, center: alkaline washing, right: water washing)

The Netherlands sediments have a significantly higher concentration of PFAS than Ancona sediments. Table 13 and Table 14 report results obtained by ECOSEDRA treatments of riverine sediments during two different experiments. In this case, very high concentrations were observed for both short-chain and long-chain PFAS in the raw sediments and the ECOSEDRA treatment was not able to completely eliminate these PFAS from the solid matrix. Particularly, the observed removals were much lower for each target PFAS compared to removal percentages observed for the Ancona sediments.

During the first ECOSEDRA experiment with Netherlands sediments, only the short-chain PFBA was detected in the acid washing solution. On the contrary, during the second experiment, the long-chain PFOS and the precursor N-EtFOSAA were detected only in alkaline solution.

Table 13: First ECOSEDRA treatment with riverine sediments

Analytes (ng/kg)	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	125	100	20%	15	<15	<15
PFBS	55	<50	100% (>9%)*	<15	<15	<15
PFOA	110	55	50%	<15	<15	<15
PFOS	1205	400	67%	<15	<15	<15
N-MeFOSAA	110	65	41%	<15	<15	<15
N-EtFOSAA	720	500	31%	<15	<15	<15
PFUdA	50	<50	100% (>0%)	<15	<15	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	2375	1120	53%	15	<15	<15

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 14: Second ECOSEDRA treatment with Netherlands sediments

Analytes (ng/kg)	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	125	<50	100% (>60%)*	<15	<15	<15
PFBS	55	<50	100% (>9%)	<15	<15	<15
PFOA	110	50	55%	<15	<15	<15
PFOS	1205	780	35%	<15	15	<15
N-MeFOSAA	110	165	0%	<15	<15	<15
N-EtFOSAA	720	1260	0%	<15	15	<15
PFUdA	50	<50	0%	<15	<15	<15
PFDS	50	75	0%	<15	<15	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	2375	2330	2%	<15	30	<15

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Overall, the release of organic material from the sediments from the Netherlands was different compared to what observed during the washing treatment of Ancona sediments. This fact can be observed by the fluorescence spectra reported in Figure 14 and Figure 15. In this case, most of the organic material was released during the alkaline treatment, and it is in agreement with the detection of PFOS and N-EtFOSAA in the alkaline washing solution. In addition, fluorescence spectra of the three liquid fractions obtained from the treatment of Netherlands sediments show the highest peak intensities in the region of the spectrum related to the presence of aromatic and proteinaceous substances. On the contrary, for the Ancona sediments, the highest fluorescence intensities were observed for humic and fulvic components (Carstea et al., 2016). Hence, differences in organic matter composition, and differences in mineral characteristics between the two kinds of sediments may be the reason of the observed differences in PFAS removal.

Figure 14: Fluorescence analysis of the first washing with Netherlands sediments

Figure 15: Fluorescence analysis of the second washing with Netherlands sediments

As a conclusive remark of the discussion, in Table 15 are reported monitored pH during the three washing steps of ECOSEDRA treatment as well as peaks of fluorescence intensities representative of different component of dissolved organic matter (Table 5) and measurements of UV absorbance at 254 nm for all the ECOSEDRA experiments described in this paragraph.

Table 15: pH, fluorescence intensities and UV (254 nm) absorbance measurements in the liquid fraction of ECOSEDRA process

Sample		pH	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	UV (254 nm)
Ancona trial 1	Acid washing	6.1	0	0.78	1.56	0.83	1.38	0.25
	Alkaline washing	11.4	0	0.49	0.68	0.66	0.55	0.15
	Final washing	9.37	0	0.51	0.27	0.30	0.24	0.05
Ancona trial 2	Acid washing	4.6	0	0.95	2.77	0.93	1.92	0.28
	Alkaline washing	11.5	0	0.72	1.14	0.57	0.86	0.10
	Final washing	9.45	0	0.39	0.46	0.28	0.35	0.04
Netherlands trial 1	Acid washing	4.8	0	0.31	0.40	0.25	0.29	0.08
	Alkaline washing	11.2	0	2.17	0.69	0.95	0.48	0.12
	Final washing	9.45	0	0.27	0.27	0.24	0.23	0.05
Netherlands trial 2	Acid washing	5.56	0	0.36	0.38	0.26	0.28	0.07
	Alkaline washing	11.2	0	3.03	0.77	1.08	0.51	0.12
	Final washing	9.85	0	0.72	0.37	0.38	0.29	0.06

3.3. Transfer and conversion of PFAS during ECOSEDRA treatment at pilot scale

After completion of the ECOSEDRA plant installation and starting of the treatment operations of sediments from Ancona Harbor at pilot scale, two sampling campaigns were planned to investigate the transfer and conversion of PFAS compounds at pilot scale. Samples were collected as indicated in Figure 16 and included raw sediments, sieved sediments, demineralized water, washed sediments stored in the storage tank, supernatant from the dewatering treatment, RO concentrate. Two sampling campaigns of sediments collection were accomplished to evaluate replicability of the treatment performance of ECOSEDRA plant.

Figure 16: Sampling points at the ECOSEDRA Pilot Plant

Results of analysis for PFAS detection in samples collected during the two sampling campaigns are reported in Table 16 and Table 17. The washing treatments performed at pilot-scale were not able to remove PFAS from the dredged sediments. PFAS reduction was lower than what observed during laboratory tests. The precursor N-EtFOSAA was completely removed during both the monitored treatment cycles, whereas the long chain PFOS was just reduced in concentration in the treated sediments during both the sampling campaigns. Reduction of PFOA was observed only during the first sampling campaign, whereas similar concentrations of PFBA were found in treated and untreated sediments.

Compared to the laboratory tests, the mixing during the washing phase was accomplished by a progressive cavity pump ($Q_{max} = 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; $H = 1 \text{ bar}$; $P = 0.37 \text{ kW}$), which operated the recirculation of the solution from the bottom to the top of the reactor. Probably, under this configuration, the washing procedure was less effective.

Table 16: First monitoring campaign of ECOSEDRA washing treatment at pilot scale

	N-EtFOSAA	PFBA	PFOA	PFOS	SUM PFAS
Raw sediment (sampling point 1) (ng/kg)	<50	300	50	210	560
Sieved sediment (sampling point 2) (ng/kg)	60	190	60	160	460
Demineralised water (sampling point 2b) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00
Acid/Alkaline washing (sampling point 3) (ng/L)	<15	40	<15	<15	40
Neutral Water washing (sampling point 4) (ng/L)	<15	63	<15	<15	63
Treated sediment (sampling point 5) (ng/kg)	<50	695	<50	55	750
Supernatant (sampling point 6) (ng/L)	<15	44	<15	<15	44
ROx concentrate (sampling point 7) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00

Furthermore, the addition of acid and soda to reach the acid or alkaline washing conditions was based on the measurements provided by a pH sensor placed in the recirculation pipe. This configuration did not allow to separate completely the acid and washing solutions. On the contrary, acid or soda were added consecutively in the same water to reach the pH conditions required for the treatment. A final washing step was performed by demineralized water by partial substitution of washing water. PFBA was detected in the liquid fractions only during the first monitored ECOSEDRA treatment cycle. PFBA was also detected during both the sampling campaigns in the liquid supernatant produced by the dewatering operation.

No PFAS were detected in the produced demineralized water or in the RO concentrate. This fact excludes PFAS contamination by the water utilized for the washing operations.

Table 17: Second monitoring campaign of ECOSEDRA washing treatment at pilot scale

	N-EtFOSAA	PFBA	PFOA	PFOS	SUM PFAS
Raw sediment (sampling point 1) (ng/kg)	<50	300	160	280	740
Sieved sediment (sampling point 2) (ng/kg)	70	200	70	160	500
Demineralised water (sampling point 2b) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00
Acid/Alkaline washing (sampling point 3) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00
Neutral Water washing (sampling point 4) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00
Treated sediment (sampling point 5) (ng/kg)	<50	385	100	55	540
Supernatant (sampling point 6) (ng/L)	<15	75	<15	<15	75
ROx concentrate (sampling point 7) (ng/L)	<15	<15	<15	<15	0.00

Fluorescence spectra were acquired from the collected liquid fractions after washing operations (i.e.; acid/alkaline washing, neutral washing) and from the supernatant coming by the dewatering treatments (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Fluorescence spectrum of waste liquid samples from pilot plant: on the left Acid/Alkaline washing, on the centre Neutral Water washing, and on the right Supernatant

Comparison of fluorescence spectra in Figure 17 with fluorescence spectra produced during laboratory tests (Figure 12 and Figure 13), highlight that spectra produced during ECOSEDRA pilot treatments show a much lower fluorescence intensities. Hence, removal of organic materials from sediments was less effective and it influenced the removal of PFAS, which probably are bound to organic matter present in the sediments.

In Table 18 are reported monitored pH during the three washing steps of ECOSEDRA treatment as well as peaks of fluorescence intensities representative of different component of dissolved organic matter (Table 5) and measurements of UV absorbance at 254 nm for all the ECOSEDRA experiments described in this paragraph.

Table 18. pH, fluorescence intensities and UV (254 nm) absorbance measurements in the liquid fractions collected at ECOSEDRA pilot plant

Sample	pH	T (°C)	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	UV (254 nm)
Acid/ Alkaline washing 3	7.8	10.7	0.832	0.639	0.315	0.186	0.176	0.04
Water washing 4	8.08	10	1.118	1.194	0.554	0.441	0.412	0.10
Supernatant 6	7.84	11.5	0.498	0.427	0.143	0.088	0.094	0.02

3.4. Transfer and conversion of PFAS by alternative washing procedures

To improve the performance of washing operations to remove PFAS, the Ancona sediments were treated adding hydrogen peroxide (30% v/v) to demineralized water with a final dosage of 2, 4 and 8 mmol of H₂O₂ per gram of dry sediment. The dosages were set according to suggestions of previous work that used hydrogen peroxide to oxidate and remove sorbed polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) from soil (Ferrarese et al., 2008).

Results of the experiments are reported in Table 19, Table 20 and Table 21. The washing with lowest H₂O₂ dosage (2 mmol H₂O₂/g) reduced PFOS under the LOQ but was not able to remove completely PFBA from the treated sediments. On the other side, washing with 4 or 8 mmol of H₂O₂ per gram of dry sediment was able to completely eliminate all detected PFAS from the treated sediments. During all the washing experiments PFBA was found in the waste liquid solutions.

Figure 18 summarizes the observed treatment performances with different H₂O₂ dosage in terms of measured sum of detected PFAS.

Table 19: Performance of washing treatment of Ancona sediments with H₂O₂ (2 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H ₂ O ₂ washing (2 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	310	90	72%	270
PFOS	140	<50	100% (>64%)	20
SUM PFAS (30)	450	90	80%	290

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 20: Performance of washing treatment of Ancona sediments with H₂O₂ (4 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H ₂ O ₂ washing (4 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	90	<50	100% (>44%)	81.4
PFOS	350	<50	100% (>86%)	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	440	<50	>89%	81.4

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 21: Performance of washing treatment of Ancona sediment with H₂O₂ (8 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H ₂ O ₂ washing (8 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	90	<50	100% (>44%)	119
PFOS	220	<50	100% (>77%)	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	310	<50	>84%	119

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Figure 18: Resume of observed performances of the H₂O₂ washings with Ancona sediments

Fluorescence analysis of the washing solutions shows that the dissolved organic material in the liquid solutions increases with the dosage of hydrogen peroxide (Figure 19). Therefore, these further experiments confirmed the trend as experienced during previous ECOSEDRA experiments. Particularly, the PFAS mobilization/removal from sediments during washing operation is correlated to the release of organic material from the solid matrix.

Figure 19: Fluorescence analysis of the H₂O₂ solution for Ancona sediments (2 mmol/g on the left, 4 mmol/g on the center, and 8 mmol/g on the right)

Hydrogen peroxide washing solutions were also used to treat sediments from Netherlands, with dosages of 2, 4 and 8 mmol H₂O₂ per gram of dry sediment. Table 22 shows that the washing with 2 mmol H₂O₂/g is not able to mobilize PFAS. Particularly, same concentration in terms of sum of PFAS was observed in the raw and treated sediments. On the other side, mobilization and removal of PFAS was much more effective when washing operations were performed with 4 and 8 mmol H₂O₂ per gram of dry sediment as shown in Table 23 and Table 24. However, these two washing conditions showed similar performances in terms of PFAS removal. PFAS compounds that experienced lower removal were PFBA (probably because PFBA is produced during oxidation process of some precursors), the long-chain PFOS and PFDS, and the precursors N-MeFOSAA and N-EtFOSAA, probably because of the stronger hydrophobic interaction with sediments/organic material of these groups of compounds.

Table 22: Performance of washing treatment of Netherlands sediments with H₂O₂ (2 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H₂O₂ washing (2 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	810	610	25%	110
PFOA	80	160	0%	<15
PFHxS	20	130	0%	<15
N-MeFOSAA	140	110	21%	<15
PFOS	1360	1860	0%	<15
N-EtFOSAA	1600	1360	15%	<15
PFDS	60	<50	100% (>17%)*	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	4020	4230	0%	110

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 23: Performance of washing treatment of the Netherlands sediments with H₂O₂ (4 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H ₂ O ₂ washing (4 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	760	940	0%	160
PFHxA	100	<50	100% (>50%)*	<15
PFBS	130	<50	100% (>62%)	<15
PFHpA	60	<50	100% (>17%)	<15
PFOA	190	<50	100% (>74%)	<15
PFHxS	110	<50	100% (>55%)	<15
N-MeFOSAA	220	90	59%	<15
PFOS	2440	620	75%	<15
N-EtFOSAA	2080	1660	20%	<15
PFDS	90	50	44%	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	6180	3360	46%	160

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Table 24: Performance of washing treatment of the Netherlands sediments with H₂O₂ (8 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	H ₂ O ₂ washing (8 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L
PFBA	410	250	39%	240
PFOA	50	<50	100% (>0%)*	<15
N-MeFOSAA	140	50	64%	<15
PFOS	1200	470	61%	<15
N-EtFOSAA	1560	910	42%	<15
PFDS	60	<50	100% (>17%)*	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	3420	1680	51%	240

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Figure 20 shows the concentration of the sum of detected PFAS in the raw and treated sediments. The lowest dosage (2 mmol H₂O₂/g) was not able to mobile the PFAS from the solid matrix. On the contrary, both 4 and 8 mmol H₂O₂/g washing shows around a 50% of “sum of PFAS” removal efficiency.

Figure 20: Performance of H₂O₂ washing with Netherlands sediments

The fluorescence analysis shows a low content of organic carbon in the H₂O₂ washing waters from Netherlands sediments for all the applied dosage. Furthermore, the addition of H₂O₂ at high concentration may have caused some quenching effect on fluorescence intensities. Nevertheless, presence of organic material is present in all generated liquid fractions.

Figure 21: Fluorescence analysis of the H₂O₂ solution for Netherlands sediments (2 mmol/g on the left, 4 mmol/g on the centre, and 8 mmol/g on the right)

Finally, the ECOSEDRA treatment was modified adding hydrogen peroxide (2 mmol H₂O₂/g) in the final washing with demineralized water in order to increase the PFAS mobilization. Comparing the ECOSEDRA treatment and the modified test in Table 25 with Ancona sediments, the removal efficiency of PFAS was significantly improved, and all detected PFAS compounds, including PFBA, were removed from the treated sediments.

Table 25: Performance of modified ECOSEDRA washing of Ancona sediments by adding H₂O₂ (2 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing (2 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	260	<50	100% (>81%)*	90	20	110
PFOS	140	<50	100% (>64%)	<15	<15	<15
SUM PFAS (30)	400	<50	100% (>88%)	90	20	110

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

In the case of Netherlands sediments, the removal efficiencies of the modified ECOSEDRA treatment (Table 26) were similar to the removals observed for the original ECOSEDRA treatment shown in Table 13 and Table 14. Particularly, it was increased significantly the concentration of PFBA in the treated sediments. Probably a greater oxidation of precursors by H₂O₂ was the reason of the increased concentration of PFBA. It is evident that Netherlands sediments have a higher load of PFAS and precursors compared to Ancona sediments.

Table 26: Performance of modified ECOSEDRA washing of Netherlands sediments adding H₂O₂ (2 mmol/g)

Analytes	Raw sediment	Treated Sediment	Removal efficiency	Acid washing	Alkaline washing	Final washing (2 mmol/g)
M.U.	ng/kg	ng/kg	%	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
PFBA	360	560	0%	30	50	80
PFBS	90	<50	100% (>44%)*	<15	<15	<15
PFOA	120	<50	100% (>58%)	<15	<15	<15
PFHxS	110	<50	100% (>55%)	<15	<15	<15
N-MeFOSAA	180	90	50%	<15	<15	<15
PFOS	2850	730	74%	20	20	40
N-EtFOSAA	2010	1750	13%	<15	40	40
SUM PFAS (30)	5720	3180	45%	50	110	160

* removal efficiencies within brackets are calculated considering the analytical LOQ

Fluorescence spectra of the produced liquid fractions for both Ancona and Netherlands sediments are reported in Figure 22 and Figure 23.

Figure 22: Fluorescence spectra of modified ECOSEDRA washings using Ancona sediments (acid solution on the left, alkaline solution on the center, and H₂O₂ solution of the right)

Figure 23: Fluorescence spectra of modified ECOSEDRA washings using Netherlands sediments (acid solution on the left, alkaline solution on the center, and H₂O₂ solution of the right)

The measured pH values, fluorescence intensities representative of different component of dissolved organic matter (Table 5) and measurements of UV absorbance at 254 nm for the modified ECOSEDRA experiments are reported in Table 27.

Table 27: pH, fluorescence intensities and UV (254 nm) absorbance measurements in the liquid fractions collected during the modified ECOSEDRA treatments

Sample	pH	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	UV 254 nm
Netherlands 2 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	6.41	0.00	0.00	0.90	0.17	0.72	0.36
Netherlands 4 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	6.19	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.04	0.34	0.34
Netherlands 8 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	6.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.08	0.58	0.59
Ancona 2 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	8.11	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.03	0.11	0.23
Ancona 4 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	7.56	0.00	0.00	0.94	0.33	0.47	1.18
Ancona 8 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	7.65	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.33	0.42	1.75
Netherlands Acid solution	6.05	0.00	0.79	0.70	0.47	0.47	0.10
Netherlands Alkaline solution	9.81	0.00	6.83	1.42	2.28	0.91	0.20
Netherlands 2 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	7.15	0.00	0.00	0.62	0.07	0.45	0.29
Ancona Acid solution	6.52	0.00	0.03	0.97	0.25	0.67	0.11
Ancona Alkaline solution	10.96	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.12	0.26	0.05
Ancona 2 mmol H ₂ O ₂ /g	8.97	0.00	0.00	0.66	0.16	0.31	0.55

3.5. Comparison of washing treatments and analysis of PFAS emission pathways to the environment

In the deliverable D3.4 “Assessing the treatment performance of PFAS degradation/ immobilisation in the liquid and solid sediment fractions: a toxicity risk assessment” will be reported data on risk assessment performed on different liquid and solid fractions generated by the ECOSEDRA sediment treatments, which will be based on CALUX test. Hence, results of this deliverable represent the background work for these next investigations.

Mandatory step of a risk assessment analysis is the exposure assessment, which has the purpose to provide the exposure metrics findings to be used for the final risk assessment. The Draft guidance on harmonised methodologies for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals produced by EFSA (2019) propose a list of “Relative Potency Factors (RPF)” to calculate total potency-adjusted exposure estimates, when multiple toxics need to be considered, such as the case of exposure to multiple PFAS compounds in a same environmental medium.

In addition, the proposal EU-COM 540/2022 amending the Directive 2000/60/EC proposes “Environmental Quality Standards” (EQS) for a group of 24 PFAS and set a threshold as “Sum of PFOA equivalent” for surface water (4,4 ng/L PFOA-EQ) and for biota or sediments in riverine/water

environments (77 ng/kg PFOA-EQ). The RPF elaborated by EFSA (2019) need to be utilized to convert PFAS in PFOA-EQ.

In agreement with the consideration above and to better compare performances in PFAS removal by the different washing treatments that have been investigated in this work, the measured concentration of all detected PFAS compounds in the different media have been converted in PFOA equivalent (PFOA-EQ) and then summed (Table 28). Calculated removal efficiencies using these data can be used to compare the different washing procedures. In addition, values of PFOA-EQ are also useful parameter to assess the most critical fractions generated by the ECOSEDRA treatment that may represent a risk for the environment and the human health.

Table 28: Concentration expressed as PFOA equivalent in raw sediments and in all solid (ng PFOA-EQ/kg) and liquid fractions (ng PFOA-EQ/L) generated by ECOSEDRA treatment

		SUM PFAS-EQ (EU-COM540/2022)
Ancona ECOSEDRA 1	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	601
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	4
	%R	95%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
	Water Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
Ancona ECOSEDRA 2	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	673
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	7
	%R	99%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	10
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	3
	Water Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	1
Ancona 2 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	296
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	5
	%R	98%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	54
Ancona 4 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	705
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	0
	%R	100%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	4
Ancona 8 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	445
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	0
	%R	100%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	6
Ancona ECOSEDRA + H₂O₂	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	293
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	0
	%R	100%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	5
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	1
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	6

		SUM PFAS-EQ (EU-COM540/2022)
Netherlands ECOSEDRA 1	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	2526
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	860
	%R	66%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
	Water Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
Netherlands ECOSEDRA 2	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	2526
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	1610
	%R	36%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	510
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	510
	Water Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	<
Netherlands 2 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	2973
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	3989
	%R	-34%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	6
Netherlands 4 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	5205
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	1387
	%R	73%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	8
Netherlands 8 mmol H₂O₂/g	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	2527
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	953
	%R	62%
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	12
Netherlands ECOSEDRA + H₂O₂	Raw Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	5904
	Treated Sediment (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	1488
	%R	75%
	Acid Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	42
	Alkaline Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	43
	H₂O₂ Washing (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	84

By the analysis of Table 28 and Figure 24, it is evident that all ECOSEDRA treatments conducted at laboratory scale with sediments from Ancona port were able to remove PFAS and respect the EQS proposed by the EU-COM 540/2022 for sediments. The addition of H₂O₂ had the only benefit to improve the removal of short-chain PFAS. Nevertheless, the produced liquid fractions showed sometimes concentration of PFOA-EQ higher than fixed EQS for surface water.

When analyzing data related to ECOSEDRA treatment cycles conducted at pilot scale (Table 29), the washing treatment was not able to reduce PFOA-EQ concentrations at level lower the established EQS by the EU-COM 540/2022. Operational procedures of washing treatment operated at pilot scale need to be improved to reach the performance obtained during laboratory tests.

Table 29: PFOA-EQ in samples collected at ECOSEDRA pilot plant

	Trial 1	Trial 2
Raw sediment 1 (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	490	740
Sieved sediment 2 (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	380	390
Distillate water 2b (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	-	-
Basic washing 3 (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	2	-
Water washing 4 (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	3.1	-
Treated sediment 5 (ng PFOA-EQ/kg)	140	230
Supernatant 6 (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	2.2	3.8
ROx concentrate 7 (ng PFOA-EQ/L)	-	-

Figure 24: Left y-axis: PFAS concentration as ng PFOA-EQ/kg measured in Ancona sediments before and after ECOSEDRA treatment conducted at laboratory scale (line red = EQS Sediment [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ dry weight] EU-COM540/2022); right y-axis: The % PFAS-EQ removed

Finally, by analyzing Table 28 and Figure 25 that report PFOA-EQ concentrations in raw and treated sediments from Netherlands, it is possible to observe that ECOSEDRA washing treatment was able to reduce significantly the calculated PFOA-EQ concentrations in the treated sediments, even though the EQS for sediments set by the EU-COM 540/2022 cannot be respected. The addition of H₂O₂ for sediment washing seems to increase the (total) observed removal of PFAS from sediments. However, due to the high heterogeneity in terms of PFAS concentrations in these sediments and possible transformation of precursors that can release PFAS compounds, the real benefit is not easy to evaluate. Indeed, sediments from Netherlands are highly contaminated by PFAS and their precursors.

Figure 25: Left y-axis: PFAS concentration as ng PFOA-EQ/kg measured in Netherlands sediments before and after ECOSEDRA treatment (line red = EQS Sediment [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ dry weight] EU-COM540/2022); right y-axis: The % PFAS-EQ removed

4. Conclusions

In this document are reported and described experimental tests accomplished to evaluate the removal of PFAS during washing treatment of dredged sediments. Particularly, we have investigated occurrence of PFAS in dredged sediments and their fate and pathways during the washing treatments implemented in the ECOSEDRA project.

ECOSSEDRA is an Italian project that aims at creating and validating at demonstrative scale (TRL > 7) an innovative technological solution for the eco-sustainable management of sediments from port dredging operations. Treated sediments from the port of Ancona will be treated and recovered as material for road embankments. Overall, the ECOSEDRA treatment procedure consists of 3 washing steps (i.e., acid washing, alkaline washing and final washing with demineralized water) with some pre-treatments (i.e., sieving to remove coarse material).

To better understand processes and mechanisms of PFAS removal and transformation during sediments washing, experimental tests have been accomplished at laboratory scale and at demo scale by sampling from the ECOSEDRA pilot plant. Furthermore, laboratory simulations of ECOSEDRA treatments have been applied to additional sediments coming from the Netherlands. Finally, experimental tests were also accomplished to evaluate the effect of the addition of H₂O₂ as amendment of the final washing step with demineralized water to improve the removal of PFAS from sediments.

Results from laboratory scale experiments have shown that removal of PFAS is mainly correlated with removal of organic material from sediments. Probably, PFAS are complexed with organic substances in the sediments and this fact highly affects their removal.

Fluorescence spectra obtained from the generated liquid fractions of ECOSEDRA process have shown that organic material content of Ancona sediments is qualitatively different from the organic material present in the sediments from Netherlands. Particularly, organic material and PFAS were better removed during the acid washing step in Ancona sediments, whereas most of organic material and PFAS were removed during the alkaline washing step in sediments from Netherlands.

ECOSSEDRA treatments applied to sediments from Ancona port were able to reduce below the LOQ long-chain PFAS such as PFOS and PFOA. However, short-chain PFAS, and particularly PFBA, were still detected in the treated sediments. The short-chain PFBA and PFPeA were found in the liquid fractions, and the highest abundance of these compounds was detected in the acid washing solution. By analysis of experimental results, it seems that some amount of short-chain PFAS in the sediments may have generated by degradation of precursors under acid or alkaline conditions. Addition of H₂O₂ during the washing process contributed to remove completely PFAS from the sediments of Ancona port. PFBA was detected in the generated liquid fractions. Oxidation of precursors by H₂O₂ may have also contributed to release this compound in the washing water solution.

Sediments from Netherlands present a much higher PFAS contamination. In this case, both short-chain and long-chain PFAS were detected in the treated sediments, and PFOS and N-EtFOSAA were detected in the alkaline washing solution. Addition of H₂O₂ increased the removal of PFAS, but short

and long-chain PFAS were still found in the treated sediments. Furthermore, after H₂O₂ addition, it has increased the amount of PFBA detected in the washing solutions.

Performances of ECOSEDRA treatment at pilot scale for washing Ancona sediments were lower than those observed at laboratory scale. Particularly, observed PFAS removals were lower than those observed at laboratory scale. This fact is surely dependent on the operational conditions utilized for mixing and recirculating the sediments within the reactor, and on the system used for the addition of acid and alkaline solutions.

Finally, PFOA equivalent concentrations, which are used for toxicity assessment studies, were calculated in raw sediments, treated sediments and generated liquid fractions for all the experimental tests accomplished in this work. Obtained concentrations were compared with the Environmental Quality Standard (EQS) proposed by the EU-COM 540/2022. ECOSEDRA treatments performed at laboratory scale were able to reach the compliance with the EQS limits for Ancona sediments, but it was not possible for sediments from Netherlands, which presented a higher level of PFAS contamination. ECOSEDRA treatments operated at pilot scale were also not able to reduce PFAS presence in sediments below the proposed EQS for sediments in surface water environments.

As a general conclusion of the performed research activities, it is possible to state that a soil-washing treatment typically utilized to remove heavy metals and hydrocarbons from contaminated dredged sediments and that include a sequence of acid, alkaline and neutral washing, can be also applied to remove PFAS compounds from sediments. However, the soil washing treatment of dredged sediments is able to assure the compliance with the EQS proposed by the draft of Directive EU-COM 540/2022 only under the following conditions:

- Low/medium contamination of PFAS in dredged sediments (i.e., for Ancona sediments, the soil washing treatment was able to assure compliance with EQS up to a contamination level of around 700 ng PFOA-EQ/kg)
- Mixing and addition of acid/alkaline solutions needs to be effectively accomplished (e.g.; ECOSEDRA pilot plant system was not able to assure appropriate mixing of sediment with washing solutions and a proper preparation of acid and alkaline waters. Those facts limited PFAS removal from sediments during pilot tests if compared with laboratory tests).

On the contrary, the soil washing treatment seems to be a non-appropriate technology for the treatment of highly contaminated sediments. It was the case of treatment of sediment from Netherlands with measured PFAS concentrations from 2000 to 6000 ng PFOA-EQ/kg. In this case, alternative treatments need to be tested. During PROMISCES research activities, thermal treatment (i.e., pyrolysis) will be tested to evaluate removal of PFAS from sediments. Results will be reported in the deliverable D3.4 (M41).

Finally, the addition of H₂O₂ during soil-washing treatment of dredged sediments may represent an effective to solution to increase the removal of PFAS from low/medium contaminated sediments.

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